
PROGRESSION OF THEORY OF ENTREPRENEURIAL MARKETING (EM)

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Abstract:

This paper analyses the theory of entrepreneurial marketing (EM), its evolution, and dimensions which are available to measure the EM. The EM theory was developed as an interface between the two major disciplines' of marketing and entrepreneurship. Researchers, scholars, and academics have been debating and nourishing the theory of EM for thirty-year period. Initially it was considered as an ideal marketing concept and strategy to enrich marketing activities and business performance of small and medium scaled enterprises (SMEs). Today, as consumers, customers and marketers, we are living in one global village and experiencing different types of buying and selling patterns. This digital era facilitates us to experience the globalization and international marketing. So far, the global market is constituted with different types and sizes of business units and those business units together generate ultimate power to handle the market and its rivalry. At present it is being declared as an enthusiastic business development factor to reach progressive levels of business life cycles without considering the size of the business unit. The purpose of this paper is to analyze development of the theory of entrepreneurial marketing based on the past literature. It consists of three parts and basic information is described by the first part. Discussion of the development of EM theory and its dimensions are considered in the second part and the Conclusions of this study are presented in the third section.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Marketing; Traditional/Conventional Marketing; Marketing Orientation; Entrepreneurial Orientation; Entrepreneurship; Entrepreneur.

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1. Introduction

To fulfill consumer and customer needs marketers have to produce not only goods and services but also they have to proceed with ongoing value creation process which produce value proportional to their consumers and customers to win and increase the market share which belong to them (Kotler, et al., Second Impression, 2011). Paradoxically marketer's way of responding to fulfill consumer needs was being changed dramatically in the entire time period of the history. Today the market is highly corrupted and rivalry moves up to the highest levels. Business diversity tends to create unlimited competition in the market place. In the past, infinite market competitions lead to create market disequilibrium and uncertainty concurrently. Some researchers contend that

the opportunities and threats in the market place are unquestionably changed by the factors of environmental turbulence, customer preferences and technology advancement. Further they say that those factors help to restrict the smoothness and flexibility of the market rivalry (Wang, et al., 2012).

However, organizational managers at the top level have to improve organizational effectiveness through creation of efficiency to face and reach success levels over the competition in the global market. As cited by Okumus,(Okumus, 2003) Kailappen said that any organization which needs to reach higher levels of efficiency and effectiveness, the management of the organization has to construct and practice organizational strategies which could achieve better performance (Hilman & Kaliappen, 2014).Further they have identified market orientation as an alternative and crucial strategy which helps firms to survive competitive, modest and uncertain business environments (Hilman & Kaliappen, 2014), (Goldman & Grinstein, 2010), They have also revealed market orientation as a marketing concept as well as a management orientation (Hilman & Kaliappen, 2014). In 2014, cited byKohil and Jaworski (1990), Kaliappen said that the market orientation can be explained by the three major components of intelligence gathering, intelligence dissemination and responsiveness, and at the same time market orientation has been presented as a marketing concept (Hilman & Kaliappen, 2014), (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990). In 1990, market orientation was described with another set of three dimensions of competitor orientation, customer orientation, and inter-functional coordination by Narver (Narver & Slater, 1990).

The world history shows dreadful economic destructions happening in countries which were considered as developed, developing and under developed by economists in the world. To overcome suffering problems, stagnant situations and to strengthen such economies, small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) were introduced as an ideal solution by some researchers, academics and governments after the World War II. Any business unit in the market place, without considering its scale, has to work out to fulfill customer needs profitably. If not, they will suffer from the symptoms of failure in the near future. To avoid such bad situations, business units in the market place have been strengthened enough to face the competition. Today entrepreneurs play a vital role to increase the power of economic engines in all the countries in the globe(Stokes & wilson, 2010). According to Lumpkin and Dess, entrepreneurial activities positively influence the business performance. (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996). On one hand the characteristics of higher risk, lack of forecasting ability, lack of opportunities and higher threats in the environment influence the organizational performance dreadfully. And on the other hand the market competition is corrupted by the dominant forces of change, complexity, confusion, and inconsistency in the internal environment of the organizations (Olannye & Eromafuru, 2016). However, global marketing was influenced by all these forces confronted from internal and external environments of the organizations and as a result the role of the customer became more of an influencing and demanding character. Unquestionably, the market is being confused by the conditions of inconsistency and bottomless rivalry. Further, they argued that the traditional/conventional marketing practices are not adequate to face increasing market demand and fulfill customer needs within that rutted market conditions. All the stakeholders who take an interest in the concept of entrepreneurial marketing, as an ideal marketing paradigm to face the unpredictable market conditions have been developing the theory of EM since 1980s. It has been derived as an interface between the two major disciplines' of marketing and entrepreneurship.

2. Objectives of the Study

This paper has been guided by the following objectives:

- 1) To distinguish the two concepts of traditional/conventional marketing and entrepreneurial marketing.
- 2) To discuss the historical and gradual development of the concept of entrepreneurial marketing.
- 3) To observe definitions which have been derived to define entrepreneurial marketing and to identify measures which available to measure the concept.

3. Research Methodology

This paper is produced as an archival study which is based on the research findings obtained from the empirical research papers and epistemological knowledge in relation to the entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurial orientation, marketing and market orientation, and entrepreneurial marketing.

4. Historical Development of Theory of Entrepreneurial Marketing

4.1. Interfaces of Marketing-Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurship-Marketing

According to some researchers, it was at the largest conference held at university of Illinois, Chicago in 1982 that the concept of entrepreneurial marketing was born, and the conference was sponsored by two of the largest professional and academic bodies, International Council for Small Business and American Marketing Association (Ionita, 2012). Further, based on the American Marketing Association's and as researchers' interest developed more, the new platform in relation to marketing and entrepreneurship was named as the marketing-entrepreneurship interface. In addition, the American Marketing Association (AMA) organized a Task Force to carry out research in relation to the development of marketing-entrepreneurship interface. Later the Task Force was introduced as a Special Interest Group (SIG) and it has worked to study an umbrella title of the marketing and entrepreneurship interface (MEI) led by professor Hills. Until 2010, marketing was being dominated by the interface between marketing and entrepreneurship and in 2010 at the 'Charleston Summit' the second discipline of entrepreneurship was dominated by the interface and thereafter this new paradigm has been evolved as entrepreneurial marketing or entrepreneurial marketing orientation until today (Ionita, 2012).

According to Chaston, the concepts of conventional marketing (administrative marketing or traditional marketing), entrepreneurship and small business marketing were recognised as different management processes until the mid-1980s, and the owner managers of SMEs, have been improving the trust of the concepts of entrepreneurship, innovation management and the management processes of small businesses since the same time period. As a result, a new marketing threshold was being developed by researchers merging the different concepts of conventional marketing, entrepreneurship, and small business marketing. As a decision maker, an SME always relies on the intuition of the owner/ manager and the powerful technique of word-of-mouth advertising rather than the formal marketing research (Chaston, 2016). SMEs never believe typical and structured frameworks within their business journey to reach the targets. Subsequently, evolution of theory and process of the entrepreneurial marketing was being commenced by

stakeholders as described below (Hills & Hultman, 2008). The following diagram (Figure 1) was developed by Chaston (Chaston, 2016), explaining the systematic development of the EM which was discussed within the paragraph.

Figure 1: Development of the Construct of Entrepreneurial Marketing
(Source: Chaston, I: Entrepreneurial Marketing-sustaining growth in all organizations, 2016)

4.2. Marketing (Traditional/ Conventional) and market orientation (MO)

The term marketing was defined as an elusive term by Stokes and it is being described both a management philosophy as needs of customers and an organizational functions of advertising, pricing, selling, and market research (Stokes, 1994). Academics, professionals and researchers have generated numerous definitions to define the term ‘marketing’ during the past several decades. However, the old sense of marketing was sale, which means ‘telling and selling’, but the new sense of marketing is satisfying customer needs by marketers. Kotler says, “Marketing is the process by which companies create value for customers and build strong customer relationships in order to capture value from customers in return” (Kotler, et al., Second Impression, 2011). It implies that marketing is a management process with five formal stages and the ultimate target of this process is creating satisfied and loyal customer base.

Basically, this value creation process is being gradually progressed in the following four stages of understanding and identifying market place; recognizing the customer needs and wants, designing a customer driven marketing strategy and construction of the integrated marketing program, developing successful relationships with customers to create and deliver superior value for them and further make them delighted and loyal customers by marketers. When it ends, the returning value from the customers is captured by marketers as profits. Though, the traditional marketing process was always based on prediction of existing markets, existing products and services. Usually it does not focus on uncertainties and risks in the segmented market.

Kilenthong (2016), said that the present marketing practices in firms have evolved during the past four decades, hence today marketing is not only a function of a firm, it has been covering broader activities by offering products, services, places, persons, ideas and causes to fulfil market

needs(Kilenthong, et al., 2016). The American Marketing Association (AMA, 2013) has defined marketing as:

“The activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large.”

Based on this definition, researches highlighted that the marketing process not only focuses to create immediate sales to fulfil customer needs, but also it works to develop integration plans to establish long-term relationships with their customer bases (Kilenthong, et al., 2016), (Schmid, 2012), (Rauch, et al., 2009). Meantime the modern view of marketing was being stimulated by the academic and research developments within the entrepreneurial and marketing behaviours. As a result, the entrepreneurial behaviours were predicted as the essence of modern marketing. Furthermore, the entrepreneurial behaviours in marketing have been acknowledged as entrepreneurial marketing by stakeholder groups(Kilenthong, et al., 2016). Market orientation was defined as an implementation of the marketing concept. In 2016, as cited by Kohli and Jaworsky (1990), Amin et al. said that the three components of intelligence generation, intelligence dissemination, and responsiveness can be defined market orientation (Amin, et al., 2016), (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990). These components were identified as MARKOR dimensions which measure the market orientation. Whether, those dimensions’ measure a firm’s ability to identify and assess customer needs and wants in potential, formal and informal market information distribution levels in the organization, and action taken to response the identified positions in the market respectively is open for discussion(Amin, et al., 2016), (Filieri & Larcker, 2015),(Kohli & Jaworski, 1990),(Kohli, et al., 1993). In 1990, three other components have been introduced to define market orientation by Narver and Slater, which was identified as a MKTOR instrument and, the three components that belong to the instrument were customer orientation, competitor orientation, and inter-functional coordination respectively (Amin, et al., 2016), (Narver & Slater, 1990). Customer orientation describes how could customers be focused on a supreme level and understanding of value chain networks, and competitor orientation says how to beat market competition when considering a firm’s strengths, weaknesses, long-term capabilities and strategies. Inter-functional coordination describes how to create greater value for target customers as a whole organization (Amin, et al., 2016),(Deshpande & Farley, 2004)(Narver & Slater, 1990),(Narver, et al., 2004).During the past three decades MO has been analysed as an effective orientation which enhances business performances by analysts (Amin, et al., 2016),(Jones & Rowley, 2011),(Deshpande, 1999),(Kohli, et al., 1993),(Narver & Slater, 1990).

4.3. Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)

In 1755, Cantillon has invented the term entrepreneur from the French term ‘entreprendre’(Burns, 2011) which means an ‘undertaker’ and was used to identify a person who does not refuse to work within risky business projects(Sledzik, 2013). In 1803, French economist Jean Baptist said that entrepreneurs shift economic resources from an area of lower productivity into an area of higher productivity to earn greater yield (Burns, 2011). Both said entrepreneurs create value through a form of change. This change may come as technology, materials, and prices or sometimes as demography. According to the Schumpeterian model of economics, when the market equilibrium exists, surrounded by the stable environmental situations, the organizational managers use traditional and conventional approaches to continue their performances. Whereas the incapability

of existing suppliers to fulfil customer needs would create unexpected disequilibrium conditions in the market. In the meantime, entrepreneurs who harness the emergent ideas which lead to create new products and industries will be fulfilling the unfulfilled customer needs and make changes in the market instabilities to create stable conditions (Chaston, 2016). In 2011, Burns defined the term entrepreneur as follows:

“Entrepreneurs use innovation to exploit or create change and opportunity for the purpose of making profit. They do this by shifting economic resources from an area of lower productivity into an area of higher productivity and greater yield, accepting a high degree of risk and uncertainty in doing so.”(Burns, 2011).

To describe and define the term entrepreneurship many perspectives are available in the literature. Creation of wealth, creation of enterprise, creation of innovation, creation of change, creation of employment, creation of value and creation of growth can be identified as most common themes used to define entrepreneurship (Kraus, et al., 2012). (Morris, et al., 2008). In 2008, the term entrepreneurship was defined by Morris et al. based on 18 keywords which were found in the literature, and it says, “entrepreneurship is a process of creating value by bringing together a unique package of resources to exploit an opportunity.”

Some researchers emphasised entrepreneurship as an essential component to establish high-performing levels of business entities in economies (Covin & Slevin, 1991). According to Schumpeter, the term entrepreneurship describes the practicing behaviour of an entrepreneur (Chaston, 2016). In 1983, the three dimensions of innovativeness, risk taking, and pro activeness were invented by Miller to describe and measure entrepreneurship (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996), (Miller, 1983). Based on these three dimensions more researchers developed scales to measure the levels of entrepreneurship (Covin & Slevin, 1991). In 1992, based on the Miller’s dimensions the four attributes of creation of a new organization, innovation, uniqueness, and growth were described as characteristics of successful entrepreneurship (Hills & laForge, 1992). In 1996, based on Miller’s three dimensions, the five behavioural characteristics which belong to an entrepreneur, namely autonomy, innovativeness, risk taking, pro activeness, and competitive aggressiveness, were described as five dimensions to measure the entrepreneurial orientation by Lumpkin & Dess (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996). Moreover, they said that, EO is being worked as a strategic orientation by covering all the behaviours, processes, practices and decision making activities to achieve business success, while the external and internal factors of the organization would work as conditional factors simultaneously. In fact, the three behavioural characteristics of innovativeness, pro activeness and risk-taking had been accepted as dimensions of EO by Kraus et al., and many other researchers (Kraus, et al., 2012), (Zahra & Garvis, 2000), (Wiklund, 1999), (Naman & Slevin, 1993) (Covin & Slevin, 1989).

On one hand Chaston (2016) said that an entrepreneur is an individual who creates a new product, process, service or venture through adopting a progressive approach. Here, he analyses who an entrepreneur is and simply visualises the role of an entrepreneur. On the other hand, some research findings have discovered that the handling and managing ways of businesses by entrepreneurs are massively different from other scales. Further it was exposed as a new strategic orientation and it was termed as the ‘entrepreneurial orientation’ (Chaston, 2016), (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996), (Jones & Rowley, 2011), (Bjerke, 2007), (Ionita, 2012), (Judith & Schmid, 2012) (Nijssen, 2014), (Amin, et

al., 2016), (Kilenthong, et al., 2015),(Kilenthong, et al., 2016), (Covin & P, 1991); and(Miller, 1983). EO has been proven as a firm's strategic orientation by research findings available since the past three decades (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996)(Covin & Selvin, 1991),(Kilenthong, et al., 2015),(Jones & Rowley, 2011),(Amin, et al., 2016),(Franco, et al., 2014),(Jones & Rowley, 2011),(Ionita, 2012),(Kilenthong, et al., 2016),(Chaston, 2016).

4.4. Entrepreneurial Marketing (EM)

Today market activities are emerging with the concept of globalization. On one hand, the global market is constituted with different types and sizes of a huge number of business units and those business units together generate ultimate power to handle the market and its rivalry, and those power sources are being identified as market forces which generate the market rivalry. And on the other hand, the complexity of the market rivalry has been enhanced by the business diversity and their behaviors. Huge number of barriers, difficulties and challenges are being created by complex market conditions especially for the small and medium scale enterprises. In order to accept and react to those challenges and continue their businesses in a pro active manner, wider market knowledge and immediate market reactions are required by the SMEs. The theory of entrepreneurial marketing (EM) was progressively developed by researchers and scholars between the two major disciplines of marketing and entrepreneurship within the past three decades. Initially EM evolved as a new marketing paradigm that facilitated SME specially to organize their marketing activities to thrive in the market competition. Even though at present the theory of EM was described as a market winning strategy for all the business units in the market place without considering its size or any other characteristic. In 2012, the two perspectives of EM have been discussed by Judithand Schmid(Judith & Schmid, 2012). According to them, the first viewpoint analyses EM as a proper marketing concept for start-up enterprises. And the second one describes EM as a concept which has behavioural characteristics of reactivity, identification and exploitation of opportunities(Judith, 2012), (Kraus, et al., 2010). Some believed EM as a construct which has the features of innovativeness, risk-taking, unplanned, and non-linear marketing actions(Judith & Schmid, 2012), (Morris, et al., 2002), Recently EMhas being described as a philosophy consisting of eight attributes of proactive innovation, opportunity driven, innovation focus, willingness to change, resource leveraging, risk management, customer intensity and value-driven (Chaston, 2016).

Figure 2: Dimensions of Entrepreneurial Marketing

(Source: Chaston, I: Entrepreneurial Marketing-sustaining growth in all organizations, 2016)

Furthermore, any organization that would like to adopt the entrepreneurial marketing orientation initially has to move to a proactive orientation from reactive, meaning hopefully they have to hunt for changes available in the external environment. And they always have to follow up new opportunities in the marketplace to grow and expand their businesses. Most of the SMEs at this level due to their smallness as well as limited capacity of key resource of financial capability, adopting new technology or skilled employees most probably would not have led to changes like growth or expansion of the business. Meantime, the attribute of resource leveraging provides an ideal solution to continue the business process with growing or expanding. The business operatives can transfer the excess resources from other functions or other products to utilize the new innovative products and services. Otherwise they can form networks with other organizations and that can provide necessary incremental resources for success. However final result from this process is value creation for the consumers and customers to fulfil their identified needs without any delay.

Definitions of Entrepreneurial Marketing

According to Ionita, during the past three decades' researchers and scholars were inventing and developing more than dozens of definitions to describe the concept of entrepreneurial marketing and there were four types of approaches used to define EM, and Ionita's study has concluded the fourth approach as the better of the four. Besides, she says that value is not created by thoughts, intentions, motivations, learning and relationships without action. She opened up the argument to define EM as behaviours, processes which create, communicate and deliver value (Ionita, 2012). The few definitions that were cited by her (Ionita, 2012), are discussed below.

“proactive identification and exploitation of opportunities for acquiring and retaining profitable customers through innovative approaches to risk management, resource leveraging and value creation.” (Morris, et al., 2002)

In addition, she has recommended this as a commonly used definition and it involves the elements of proactivity, opportunity, risk taking and innovativeness which relate to entrepreneurship as well as the elements of customer focus, resource leveraging, guerrilla marketing and value creation which relate to marketing. Then she argued that it is appropriate enough to understand fragmented, dynamic and hostile business context. Then the definition presented by Kraus et al., had been cited and according to Ionita, they mainly focused on marketing rather than entrepreneurship as a discipline. The processes of satisfying and managing customer relationships were stimulated by the characteristics of innovativeness, risk taking and pro activeness (Ionita, 2012).

“EM is an organizational function and a set of processes for creating, communicating and delivering value to customers and for managing customer relationships in ways that benefit the organisation and its stakeholders and that is characterized by innovativeness, risk-taking, pro-activeness, and may be performed without resources currently controlled.”(Kraus, et al., 2010) Besides, she had paid her attention to a second type of definitions cited by Morrish, et al., (2010) and Schindehutte and Morris, (2010). Those were identified as the second type and more radical than the above definitions. These definitions were derived basically depend on both the disciplines of marketing and entrepreneurship. The definition was;

“the construct of EM is not simply the nexus between the sets of marketing and entrepreneurial processes that has emerged as the conventional conceptualization of EM, but fully includes all aspects of administrative marketing and entrepreneurship.”(Morrish, et al., 2010)

Further, the EM was defined as a strategic orientation as well an extension of the marketing function by Schindehutte and Morris(Schindehutte & Morris, 2010).

According to Ionita, the third type of definitions ascertains EM as an alternative concept to traditional marketing while having more innovative marketing tools, such as guerrilla marketing, radical marketing, expeditionary marketing, disruptive marketing (Ionita, 2012). Then the forth type of definitions are discussed sticking basically to the company lifecycle. Thereby she describes, that an informal type of marketing was practised in the early stages of a firm’s lifecycle due to the smallness and resource limitations. This was introduced as EM. When the company is growing, it makes the applicable marketing practices more complex, rigorous, structured and formalized. This was introduced as formalized marketing. Then the company has reached the mature level more complex formalized marketing will have to be applied. Further she said that the concept of EM was not related to the firm size and its lifecycle. Finally, she summarized EM as a set of processes of creating, communicating and delivering value, guided by effectual logic and used in highly uncertain business environments. Further EM was remarked as an approach to overcome obstacles, and respond to challenges (Ionita, 2012).

Entrepreneurial marketing was emphasised as an adaptation theory to fulfil the distinctive needs, and many issues of opportunity, innovation, risk and resource constraints in SMEs are simultaneously addressed by some researchers (Becherer, et al., 2012). However, in 2016, Cacciolotti & Lee, revealed entrepreneurial marketing as an alternative marketing management approach which enables to improve the SMEs marketing activities. Further they have defined ‘Entrepreneurial Marketing’ as below:

“Entrepreneurial marketing entails the proactive identification and exploitation of opportunities for acquiring and retaining profitable customers through innovative approaches to risk management, resource leveraging and value creation”.

In 2011, Kurgan, et al. cited some research findings, that differentiated the processes of entrepreneurial marketing and traditional marketing, as a result the fourteen differences had been found between the two processes(Morris, et al., 2002),(Morris & Kuratko, 2002),(Stokes, 2000). Thereby he believed that the processes of value creation and customer satisfaction were focused in traditional marketing whereas the entrepreneurial marketing focuses on innovations, and it works to satisfy customer needs by creating innovative values (Kurgun, et al., 2011). The following table differentiates between traditional and entrepreneurial marketing (Stokes, 2000).

Table 1: Differences between Entrepreneurial Marketing and Traditional Marketing Concepts; source:(Stokes, 2000)

Marketing principles	Traditional Marketing	Entrepreneurial Marketing
Concept	Customer-oriented: Market-driven, product development follows	Innovation-oriented: Idea-driven, intuitive assessment of market needs.

Strategy	Top-down segmentation, targeting and positioning.	Bottom-up targeting of customers and other influence groups.
Methods	The marketing mix: four and seven Ps.	Interactive marketing methods: word-of-mouth marketing (WOM)
Market intelligence	Formalised research and intelligence systems	Informal networking and information gathering

Kilenthong et al., showed that a firm’s marketing activities are influenced by its level of entrepreneurship (Kilenthong, et al., 2016). According to Schmid and Judith, (2012), it’s very rare to identify generally accepted quantitative measurements of EM. Though, most of the scholars and researchers are continuously concerned during the past three decades to determine underlying dimensions to the construct of ‘Entrepreneurial Marketing’, and further to invent conceptual frameworks and models in quantitative manner to analyse and measure the orientation of ‘Entrepreneurial Marketing’. Nevertheless, some of them paid attention to identify the underlying dimensions of EM by developing qualitative frameworks and models. Ultimately entrepreneur’s behavioural characteristics were identified as the underlying dimensions to the ‘EM’ by both groups until today.

The concept of EM was detailed from a “conceptual framework for entrepreneurial marketing” which was based on four pillars of entrepreneurship, resources, actors and processes by Bjerke and Hultman (2002) [Figure No..]. It shows the relationships between the four pillars and the pillar of entrepreneurship and explains why and how opportunities could be recognised, and employed in order to increase customer value. The next pillar, the resources, considers as an essential element to generate value to the customer. All the processes together have been assembled as one, by the third pillar of processes, to create greater value propositions to the customer. And the last pillar of actors represents individuals or organizations that direct and run all the processes to create customer value. Thereby the concept of EM was identified as a concept which combined transactional and relationship marketing (Bjerke & Hultman, 2002).

Figure-3-Four Pillars of the Entrepreneurial Marketing Framework, Source: (Bjerke & Hultman, 2002)

In 2002, seven dimensions were identified to measure EM by Morris, Schindehutte, & LaForge. The seven underlying dimensions to the Entrepreneurial Marketing were revealed by them under three main categories. Then the pro-activeness, opportunity-focused, risk-taking, and innovation-

oriented were expressed as underlying dimensions to the entrepreneurial orientation (EO). Further they said, those behavioural characteristics of an entrepreneur has directed the firm to entrepreneurial orientation. Customer intensity, and value creation were exposed as underlying dimensions to the market orientation and those behavioural characteristics of an entrepreneur give an appearance of market orientation to the firm. Finally, they focused on one single dimension of resource leveraging. In the end, they supposed that the SME can be employed in each of these dimensions having a greater or lesser degree of contribution(Morris, et al., 2002). In 2004, quantitative measuring of EM was accomplished based on the research findings of Morris et al. (2002), by Kocak(Kocak, 2004).

However, the model developed by Morris, Schindehutte, and LaForge in 2002 was applied massively by academics and researchers in their research studies to measure the magnitude levels of inter-relationships which exist between the dimensions of EM within the past three decades. Further the model has been utilized to measure inter-relationships and causal relationships which exist between the entrepreneurial marketing orientation (EMO) and levels of performance of SMEs as well as to calculate and analyse linearity and correlation positions.

The 'EMICO' framework had been developed by Jones and Rowley in 2009, to measure the entrepreneurial marketing orientation in SMEs. Thereby the fifteen (15) dimensions were being introduced to measure the entrepreneurial marketing orientation by this framework. The four orientations of entrepreneurial orientation (EO), market orientation (MO), innovation orientation (IO), and customer/ sales orientation (CO/SO) were considered as the underlying basis for the invention of the 'EMICO' framework(Jones & Rowley, 2009). In 2011, merging the four orientations, the "EMO" conceptual model was derived by them on the platform of "EMICO" framework and to measure EMO the fifteen dimensions were defined by them. These fifteen dimensions expanded respectively the four main strategic orientations of: market orientation (MO): responsiveness towards customers, communication with customers, understanding and delivering customer value; entrepreneurial orientation (EO): research and development, speed to market, risk taking, pro-activeness; innovation orientation and(IO): overarching knowledge infrastructure, encouraging, stimulating and sustaining innovation(Jones & Rowley, 2011).The four strategic orientations of EO, CRO, MO, and IO were proven as determinants of the EMO model by Jones & Rowley in 2011 and Reijonen in 2012(Jones & Rowley, 2011);(Reijonen, 2012).

According to researchers, EM behaviours are widely reported and these behaviours were concerned as dimensions of the EM construct, but no common agreement on a numerical number of the behavioural dimensions needed to measure the construct of EM was reached. In 2002, Morris et al. introduced seven dimensions, and in 2013, Jones et al revealed the framework with fifteen dimensions as determinants to measure the construct of 'Entrepreneurial Marketing' In 2015, Kilenthong et al., categorized the literature into two research teams, and he showed that first team confirmed the seven dimensions' model which was invented by Morris et al in 2002, (Fiore et al., 2013; Kocak, 2004; Schmid, 2012) and the second team believed the EM frameworks which created by scholars (Mort et al, 2012) (Jones & Rowley, 2013)(Kilenthong, et al., 2016). Based on the seven factor model, of Kilenthon get al. (2015) the six dimension model has been developed and exposed dimensions were growth orientation, opportunity orientation, total customer focus, value creation through networks, informal market analysis, and closeness to the market(Kilenthong, et al., 2015).

The models and frameworks which were derived to measure the construct of entrepreneurial marketing (EO) or entrepreneurial marketing orientation (EMO) by researchers in different time periods is summarised in the following table.

Table 2: Dimensions which Available to Measure the Construct of Entrepreneurial Marketing

Bjerke&Hultman (2002) (Very Basic Type)	Based on Morris, Schindehutte&LaForge (2002)-Quantitative models (the seven dimensions model)	Jones & Rowley (2009, 2011)-Qualitative framework & model	Kilenthong et al. 2015 The six factor model
<p>Four pillars including: Opportunities and value creation: Entrepreneurship Resources Actors Processes</p>	<p>1. The seven dimensions' model based on Morris., (2002) EO and MO (market orientation) and resource leveraging <u>EO-four dimensions</u> Proactiveness Risk-taking Innovativeness Opportunity-focus <u>MO-two dimensions</u> Customer intensity Value creation <u>Resource leveraging</u> EO+MO dimensions + resource leveraging (04+02+01=07) 2. The five factor model based on the seven factor model 3. The six factor model based on the five and seven factor models by Kilenthong et al., (2015</p>	<p>Fifteen dimensions based on EO, MO, IO (innovation orientation), CO/SO (customer/ sales orientation)-this framework is identified as 'EMICO framework'. Based on the EMICO the EMO (Entrepreneurial Marketing Orientation) conceptualized model was invented by Jones & Rowley in 2011. <u>EO-Research & development, speed to market, risk taking, proactiveness,</u> <u>MO- exploiting markets, market intelligence generation, responsiveness towards competitors, integration of business process, networks and relationships</u> <u>IO- knowledge infrastructure, propensity to innovate,</u> <u>CO- responsiveness toward customers, communication with customers, understanding and delivering customer value, promotion and sales.</u></p>	<p>Six dimensions to measure the construct of EM Growth orientation (GO) Opportunity orientation Total customer focus Value creation through networks Informal market analysis Closeness to the market</p>

5. Conclusions

This study attempted to analyse development of the theory of entrepreneurial marketing and its progressive levels. Some of existing literature says that EM was developed as a most suitable marketing concept to apply for SMEs and new ventures. In parity with this idea they suggest that the features of SME marketing are entirely different from other scales of businesses. Because of other levels, such as medium and large scales that they have organizational structures as well as structured criteria to apply to reach their targeted goals. But SMEs, most probably do not have structures and written plans, just they are keeping everything only in their minds, and further they have worked to succeed on characteristics of owner-manager's skills, abilities, attitudes business environment and resources (Blankson & Stokes, 2002). In accordance with existing literature traditional marketing had always worked to satisfy customer needs by producing marketing offers, and it does not seek owner manager's behavioural characteristics'. In contrast to traditional marketing, entrepreneurial marketing is conceptualized as a particular type of marketing and it is based on the behavioural characteristics of innovativeness, risk-taking, and pro activeness of entrepreneur as well as organizational resources and market opportunities. However, in new era with the concept of globalization and new technology EM will have high potential for development in the near future. Most researchers believe that EM is not only for the SMEs and new ventures but also irrespective of firm size, or age or other characteristic it can be implemented for any firm or business to reach their targeted goals. Therefore, few of definitions were discussed in relation to the concepts of entrepreneurial marketing and traditional marketing. Latter part of this paper has discussed the dimensions which available in the past literature to measure the EM. Specially the four pillars by Bjerke et al.(Bjerke & Hultman, 2002), and the seven dimension model by Morris et al.(Morris, et al., 2002), the 'EMICO' framework and the 'EMO' model (Jones & Rowley, 2009), (Jones & Rowley, 2011), and the six dimensions model by Kilenthong et al. (Kilenthong, et al., 2015), (Kilenthong, et al., 2016) were discussed.

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